

The Impact of Stitch Types on Seam Strength for Polyester-Cotton Blended Apparel

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to investigate the impact of sewing thread types and stitch types on seam strength and efficiency of superimposed seam for pc blended apparel. An experimental stylisme was used for the study including four types of thread and two stitch classes for pc blended apparel. The performance properties were seam strength and efficiency which is investigated. The seam strength and efficiency of the fabric were determined by using the tensile testing machine. Inferential statistics (Analysis of Variance at 0.05 alpha levels) were used for data analysis. The results of this experiment showed that differences existed between the four thread types with regard to seam strength and efficiency, Polyester-wrapped thread with a polyester filament core thread shows better seam strength and Seam Efficiency in four stitch types than other for pc blended fabrics. The current study has revealed the behavior of seams in the different stitch and threads of Polyester cotton blended fabric. Analysis of Variance(One-way) at 0.05 alpha levels) were employed in testing the hypotheses since they are measures used in measuring differences, and the purpose of this study was to establish if any difference existed between and among the stitch types of same class and thread types which was involved in the study. Finally this research will have a scope to search the best sewing thread in terms of stitch types with high seam performance as well as for the development of our apparel sector.

Keywords: Apparel, polyester cotton blended, performance, properties, seam strength, seam efficiency.

INTRODUCTION

In apparel products, seams are formed when two or more pieces of fabrics are held together by stitches. As the seam is one of the basic components for the construction of apparel, seam quality has great importance in apparel product. The line or shape of apparel depends largely on the way the sections are joined which is seam. Stitches and their resulting seams are part of the crucial elements of apparel construction. Though seams quality contributes to better performance of the apparel during end use and contributing to the overall quality of the sewn apparel. Performances of the seam are reliant on the quality of sewing threads and their vivacious behavior. Quality is one aspect that consumers are lookout for in an apparel product; though it varies from individual to individual. Quality seams in sewn apparel contribute to the overall performance of the apparel in use. Poor quality seam makes apparel unusable even though the fabric may be in good condition. Seams are formed through stitches and stitches are formed with sewing thread comprising important sewing parameter setting of sewing machines. Once a fabric has been selected and cut for a particular apparel item, the next thing is to shape the flat fabric pieces to the desired three-dimensional form [1]. Seams, darts, and dart equivalents are the means used to create that third dimension. Thread stitching is the method used almost exclusively to secure shaping devices; therefore, the appearance and durability of any seam, dart or tuck depends on the stitches [1]. In the apparel industry, seam quality mainly defined through various functional and aesthetic performances anticipated for the apparel product during their end use [2]. The Seam enhances serviceability and durability for functional performance of the fabric both the functional and aesthetic

performance of an apparel product in terms of durability and stability are affected by seam strength [3]. The length of life of a seam in apparel should be as long as that of the other materials and both should be appropriate to the required end use of the apparel. The seam can be considered to have failed in durability terms, if either the thread or the fabric in the seam fails at an early stage. For manufacturers to be able to select appropriate thread types and a stitch density to achieve quality in seams, conditions is exposed to during use must also be examined [4]. The thread types used in stitching, its construction, size and finishing influence the seam strength of apparel [5]. Seam strength and efficiency of the fabric stitched with coarser yarn was higher than the fabric stitched with finer yarn [6]. The range of sewing threads available on the market has recently increased significantly with sewing threads of cotton and polyester being the most commonly used in the manufacture of apparels [7]. Quality apparel must perform satisfactorily in normal use, meaning that apparel must be able to withstand normal wearing and care without seams coming apart, color fading and fabric tearing [7]. Seam strength is an important factor in determining the durability of apparel. Seam strength is determined by resistance to pulling force and abrasion. Seam tenacity breaks the fabric or the weakest stitch of seam. Seam abrasion resistance is the amount of rubbing action needed to wear away stitches in the seam strength is related to stitch type, thread strength, and thread tension, seam type, seam efficiency, width and stitches per inch [5]. Seam engineering, the determination of the best stitch type, seam configuration and thread type which should be used for a particular assembly requires a thorough knowledge of many variables. The inappropriate choice of any one element can cause

in failure of the sewn seam and finally failure of the final product [8]. The quality and performance of a sewn garment depend on various seaming factors such as seam strength; slippage, puckering, appearance and yarn severance. Seam appearance and its strength have to be proper, for a perfect fitting and look of apparel [5]. Nevertheless, the type of thread used is influenced by the fabric used but in some instances manufacturers of apparels do not pay much consideration to the thread types and fabrics. Meeting the requirements for SPIs by using the right type of thread for a particular fabric helps to achieve quality and enhances the apparels' performance in use. An understanding of quality and performance of fabrics and apparel products will aid in achieving a vibrant industry [9]. Tensile properties of a seam define the steadiness of products construction to deformation and are characterized through the strain strength in cross direction, elongation in direction of the seam and the bending stiffness [10]. The seam strength can be affected by the changes of seam and stitch type because it affects the interlacing of sewing thread with yarns in the fabric [11]. A failed seam makes the apparel unwearable even though the fabric is still in good condition, for this reason it is very important to relate sewing parameters to fabric properties. This is measured by using the following equation:

$$S_s = K \times S_b$$

Where:

S_s = sewn seam strength (N)

K = a Constant equal to 1000 for SI units

A lot of studies have been done to determine the seam strength according to ASTM 1683-04 standards, which express the value of seam strength in terms of maximum force in Newton (N) to cause a seam specimen to rupture. Determine percent seam efficiency using below formula:

$$E = 100 S_s / F_b$$

Where:

E = seam efficiency, %

S_s = sewn seam strength, N (lbf), and

F_b = fabric breaking force, N (lbf).

The following specific objectives will be addressed in this study:

1. To investigate the performance of seams constructed with different sewing threads with stitch types.
2. To find out the effect of various stitches on seam strength and efficiency.
5. To determine the significant level of impact of stitch on seam strength and efficiency using data analysis

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Selection of Seam:

Superimposed seam was selected for this study.

Selection of Thread:

To investigate the impact of different stitches on seam strength for polyester-cotton blended fabric, four different types of thread were used for the seam constructions. To make apparels these threads are commonly used. These threads are composing of different fiber. These threads consist of below composition which is mentioned in table 2.1. All threads are collected from coats, Bangladesh.

Table (2.1): Thread construction

T1	100% staple spun polyester thread	27
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T2	Polyester core spun with cotton wrap	30
T3	100% Cotton	30
T4	Polyester-wrapped thread with a polyester filament core	30

Fabric selection and testing:

One fabric was collected for this study from Bangladeshi manufacturer. Table 2.2 represents the fabric construction.

Table (2.2) – Fabric construction

Fabric ID	Fabric type	Fabric Weight (g/m ²)	Yarn count		Fabric construction	
			warp	weft	EPI	PPI
F	65% Polyester 35% Cotton Blend	96	45	45	141	71

Selection of Sewing Parameters:

ASTM D 1683 – 04 method put emphasis on that if fabric mass up to 270 g/m² then Stitch density should be (4.7±1/2) stitches per centimeter or (12 ±1/2 stitches per inch) and Needle Size should be Metric 90 as Standard for seam preparation for seam strength test. From the table 2.2 it was observed that collected fabrics weight were below 270 (g/m²) for this reason stitch density 12 and Needle size Metric 90 were selected for seam preparation.

Selection of stitch types:

Two stitch classes were chosen for this study. Two types of stitch were selected from each class. They are:

- ❖ Stitch Class 300 lockstitch (301 and 304)
- ❖ Stitch Class 400 Multi thread chain stitch (401 and 406)

Seam strength: Preparation and evaluation

For seam strength test, the fabric was prepared according to Method **ASTM D 1683 – 04**

Standard Test Method for Failure in Sewn Seams of Woven Apparel Fabrics.

- ❖ About 160 samples were obtained by randomly cutting for this fabric. Fabric was cut to dimensions of 350 mm by 100 mm with their long dimensions parallel both warp direction and filling direction. Then the fabric was fold 100 mm from one end and then sewn with a seam allowance of 20 mm.
- ❖ After seaming, from 20 mm the fold was cut by 8 mm for opening. Five samples were prepared for each test according to method.
- ❖ The test specimen was contain a seam approximately 100 mm (4 in.) from one end and each test specimen will contain sufficient material for one seamed and one fabric test.
- ❖ Seam strength was tested using the **Tinius Olsen tester** according to method **ASTM D1683 – 04**.
- ❖ The following parameters were set for testing.
 - Load Range : 1124 lbf
 - Extension Range : 39.37 in
 - Test Speed : 12.00 in/min
 - Pre load : 1.00 lbf
 - Jaw separation : 75 mm
- ❖ In the open front position place the specimen into the clamp

with the seam line centrally located between the clamp faces and perpendicular to the pulling force.

- ❖ To aid in placing specimens into the testing machine, it was recommended to draw vertical alignment guides perpendicular to the stitch line 40 mm (1.5 in.) from both edges. To set top and bottom jaws of equal width, measuring from the edge to perpendicular lines drawn on the specimen can make sure proper placement in the clamps.
- ❖ Then Adjustment was done for the distance between the clamps at the start of the test at 75 ± 3 mm.
- ❖ To calculate the sewn seam specimen, observe and record whether the seam rupture is caused by (1) fabric yarn rupture, (2) sewing thread rupture, (3) sewn seam yarn slippage, or (4) a combination of two or more of the foregoing.
- ❖ Maximum force needed to break the seam perpendicular to the direction of extension was recorded. Observation was made in order to make sure that the seam failure is due to break not due to fabric tears. It is observed that all seams were rupture at the seam line due to sewing thread breakage.
- ❖ The mean of the recorded maximum forces for seams to rupture for all samples of one fabric was calculated.

Selection of Sewing Machine:

Below Table 2.3 shows sewing machines are used for stitching test samples.

Table 2.3: Machine list

Machine Name	stitch type
Industrial lock stitch machine	301
Industrial zigzag lock stitch machine	304

single needle chain stitch machine	401
Flat lock machine	406

ANALYSIS OF EXPERIMENTAL DATA

Result was documented for each of the tests identified for stitched and unstitched specimens. The statistical means that was used in the analysis of the data collected was the Software Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for Windows version 20. Means were used to describe if any difference existed between the strength of the four threads for three fabrics obtaining seam strength testing result. For testing the hypotheses Analysis of Variance(One-way) at 0.05 alpha levels were used since they are measures used in measuring differences, and the reason of this study was to establish if any difference existed between and among the stitch types of same class and thread types. One-Way ANOVA was used for the test of hypotheses 1(a,b) and 2 (a,b) where each independent variable (thread type : T1,T2,T3 and T4) was taken against the dependent variables (stitch type:301,304,401,406).

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Seam Strength and Efficiency for Stitch classes of PC blended fabric:

Seam Strength for Stitch class 300:

Seam Strength for F Fabric in both warp and filling directions is shown in Table (3.1) for Stitch class 300 (type 301 and 304).T4 thread shows better seam strength in both types of stitch which is made from Polyester-wrapped thread with a polyester filament core thread. T1 thread shows lowest strength than T1 and T2 for 301 but in 304 stitch types T3 shows lowest strength than T1 and T2. Multiple Bar diagram (Fig 3.1) also shown on below table. Stitch type 301 shows better strength compared to stitch type 304.

Table (3.1): Seam strength test result for Stitch class 300

Mean Seam Strength								
	WARP (lbf)				FILLING (lbf)			
Thread/stitch	T1	T2	T3	T4	T1	T2	T3	T4
301	28.25	34.43	35.924	43.47	28.07	34.05	34.29	39.78
304	26.76	33.94	23.58	37.83	27.76	33.86	20.84	35.82

Fig 3.1: Mean Seam Strength

Seam Efficiency for Stitch class 300

Seam Strength of pc blended fabric in both warp and filling directions is shown in Table (3.2) for Stitch class 300 (type 301 and 304). From the table it was observed that all stitches have higher seam efficiency in warp direction compared to filling direction. T4 thread shows better seam efficiency in both types of

stitch which is made from Polyester-wrapped thread with a polyester filament core thread. T1 thread shows lowest strength than T1 and T2 for 301 but in 304 stitch types T3 shows lowest efficiency than T1 and T2. Multiple Bar diagram (Fig 3.2) also shown on below table. Overall, Stitch type 301 shows better efficiency compared to stitch type 304.

Table (3.2): Seam Efficiency test result for Stitch class 300

Mean Seam Efficiency (%)								
	WARP				FILLING			
THREAD/STITCH	T1	T2	T3	T4	T1	T2	T3	T4
301	51.79	64.414	64.12	79.79	43.626	50.854	51.356	60.686
304	48.658	58.126	47.602	71.952	47.268	51.95	37.234	32.882

Fig 3.2: Mean Seam Strength

Seam Strength for Stitch class 400

Seam Strength for F Fabric in both warp and filling directions is shown in Table (3.3) for Stitch class 400 (type 401 and 406). Overall, All stitches have higher seam strength in warp direction compared to filling direction. T4 thread shows better seam strength in stitch type 401 which is made from Polyester-

wrapped thread with a polyester filament core thread. T2 thread also shows better strength than T1 and T3. T3 thread shows lowest strength than others for both stitches. Multiple Bar diagram (Fig 3.3) also shown on below table. Stitch type 401 shows much closer strength compared to stitch type 406.

Table (3.3): Seam strength test result for Stitch class 400

Mean Seam Strength								
	WARP (lbf)				FILLING (lbf)			
THREAD/STITCH	T1	T2	T3	T4	T1	T2	T3	T4
401	35.27	43.968	29.81	51.05	31.94	42.526	26.194	49.412
406	37.91	36.312	24.42	51.22	36.63	31.30	22.45	46.79

Seam Efficiency for Stitch class 400

Seam Efficiency for Fabric F in both warp and filling directions is shown in Table (3.4) for Stitch class 400 (type 401 and 406). Overall, All stitch has higher seam Efficiency in warp direction compared to filling direction. T4 and T2 thread shows better seam Efficiency in both types of stitch which is made from Polyester-

wrapped thread with a polyester filament core thread. T3 thread also shows lowest strength than T1 and T2. Multiple Bar diagram (Fig 3.4) also shown on below table. Stitch type 401 shows better efficiency compared to stitch type 406 for Fabric Id F in both warp and filling directions is shown in below table.

Table (3.4): Seam Efficiency test result for Stitch class 400

Mean Seam Efficiency (%)								
Thread/Stitch	WARP				FILLING			
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T1	T2	T3	T4
401	66.12	81.51	55.046	90.318	47.20	64.056	40.16	75.174
406	66.85	60.50	44.52	81.40	58.78	55.07	33.86	67.99

Fig 3.4: Average Seam efficiency

Comparison between stitch class 300 with thread for Fabric ID F:For Warp:

In this study, four types of thread are taken for comparison with

stitch class 300. Statistical One way ANOVA test was used for doing this comparison. In table 3.5 the outcome is presented:

Table 3.5: CLASS 300, Seam Strength (WARP)

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
T1	Between Groups	5.595	1	5.595	1.654	.234
	Within Groups	27.067	8	3.383		
	Total	32.662	9			
T2	Between Groups	.615	1	.615	.229	.645
	Within Groups	21.461	8	2.683		
	Total	22.076	9			
T3	Between Groups	380.936	1	380.936	155.812	.000
	Within Groups	19.559	8	2.445		
	Total	400.495	9			
T4	Between Groups	79.580	1	79.580	21.695	.002
	Within Groups	29.346	8	3.668		
	Total	108.926	9			

The results from Table 3.5 showed the analysis the seam strength of fabric ID F in warp direction.

Comments: From One-way ANOVA it is found that thread type T1 and T2 have the significance value (P-value): 0.234 & 0.645 is greater than alpha (.05) value, thus null hypothesis is accepted.

For Thread Type T3 and T4 the significance value (P-value):0.000 & 0.002 are less than alpha (.05) value, thus null hypothesis is rejected.

Decision: The null hypothesis is accepted for thread T1 and T2, which means there is no significant difference between thread type T1 and T2 with seam strength of stitch class 300. The null hypothesis is rejected for thread T3 and T4, which means there is significant difference between thread T3 and T4 with seam strength of stitch class 300.

Seam Efficiency

In this study, four types of thread are taken for comparison with stitch class 300 of Fabric F. In table 3.6 the outcome is presented:

Table 3.6: CLASS 300, SEAM EFFICIENCY (WARP)

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
T1	Between Groups	24.524	1	24.524	2.455	.156
	Within Groups	79.900	8	9.988		
	Total	104.424	9			
T2	Between Groups	98.847	1	98.847	17.066	.003
	Within Groups	46.337	8	5.792		
	Total	145.185	9			
T3	Between Groups	376.014	1	376.014	10.232	.013
	Within Groups	293.999	8	36.750		
	Total	670.014	9			
T4	Between Groups	153.586	1	153.586	9.605	.015
	Within Groups	127.918	8	15.990		
	Total	281.504	9			

The results from Table 3.6 showed the analysis the seam efficiency of fabric ID F in filling direction.

Comments: From One-way ANOVA we found that thread type T1 have the significance value (P-value): 0.156 is greater than alpha (.05) value, thus null hypothesis is accepted.

For Thread Type T2, T3 and T4 the significance value (P-value):.003, 0.13 & .015 are less than alpha (.05) value, thus null hypothesis is rejected.

Decision: The null hypothesis is accepted for thread T1 which means there is no significant difference for thread types T1 with seam efficiency of stitch class 300 for fabric F.

The null hypothesis is rejected for thread T2, T3 and T4, which means there is significant difference between thread type T2, T3 and T4 with seam efficiency of stitch class 300 for fabric F.

For Filling:

In this study, four types of thread are taken for comparison with stitch class 300 of Fabric F. In table 3.7 the outcome is presented:

Table 3.7: CLASS 300, Seam Strength (FILLING)

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
T1	Between Groups	.253	1	.253	.069	.799
	Within Groups	29.196	8	3.650		
	Total	29.449	9			
T2	Between Groups	.090	1	.090	.056	.819
	Within Groups	12.940	8	1.617		
	Total	13.030	9			
T3	Between Groups	452.391	1	452.391	43.582	.000
	Within Groups	83.041	8	10.380		
	Total	535.432	9			
T4	Between Groups	278.678	1	278.678	3.957	.082
	Within Groups	563.472	8	70.434		
	Total	842.151	9			

The results from Table 3.7 showed the analysis the seam strength of fabric ID F in filling direction.

Comments: from One-way ANOVA we found that thread type T1, T2 and T4 have the significance value (P-value): 0.799, 0.819 & 0.082 which are greater than alpha (.05) value, thus null hypothesis is accepted.

For Thread Type T3 the significance value (P-value):0.000 is less than alpha (.05) value, thus null hypothesis is rejected.

Decision: The null hypothesis is accepted for thread T1, T2 and T4, which means there is no significant difference between

thread type T1, T2 and T4 with seam strength of stitch class 300 for fabric F.

The null hypothesis is rejected for thread T3 which means there is significant difference for thread type T3 with seam strength of stitch class 300 for fabric F.

Seam Efficiency:

ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
T1	Between Groups	5.898	1	5.898	.651	.443
	Within Groups	72.537	8	9.067		
	Total	78.435	9			
T2	Between Groups	11.088	1	11.088	3.348	.105
	Within Groups	26.492	8	3.311		
	Total	37.580	9			
T3	Between Groups	1.505	1	1.505	.121	.737
	Within Groups	99.623	8	12.453		
	Total	101.128	9			
T4	Between Groups	809.820	1	809.820	19.170	.002
	Within Groups	337.947	8	42.243		
	Total	1147.767	9			

The results from Table 3.8 showed the analysis the seam efficiency of fabric ID F in filling direction.

Comments: From One-way ANOVA we found that thread type T1, T2 and T3 have the significance value(P-value): 0.443, 0.105 and 0.737 which are greater than alpha (.05) value, thus null hypothesis is accepted.

For Thread Type T4 the significance value (P-value):.002 is less than alpha (.05) value, thus null hypothesis is rejected.

Decision: The null hypothesis is accepted for thread T1, T2 and T3 which means there is no significant difference between thread

type T1,T2 and T3 with seam efficiency of stitch class 300 for fabric F.

The null hypothesis is rejected for thread T4, which means there is significant difference between thread types T4 with seam efficiency of stitch class 300 for fabric F.

Comparison between stitch class 400 with thread for Fabric ID F:

For Warp:

In this study, four types of thread are taken for comparison with stitch class 400. Statistical One way ANOVA test was employed for doing this comparison. In table 3.9 the outcome is presented:

Table 3.9: CLASS 400, Seam Strength (WARP)

ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
T1	Between Groups	17.450	1	17.450	2.903	.127
	Within Groups	48.092	8	6.011		
	Total	65.542	9			
T2	Between Groups	401.449	1	401.449	16.519	.004
	Within Groups	194.423	8	24.303		
	Total	595.872	9			
T3	Between Groups	72.738	1	72.738	22.185	.002
	Within Groups	26.230	8	3.279		
	Total	98.968	9			
T4	Between Groups	11.067	1	11.067	1.521	.252
	Within Groups	58.214	8	7.277		
	Total	69.281	9			

The results from Table 3.9 showed the analysis the seam strength of fabric ID F in warp direction.

Comments: From One-way ANOVA we found that thread type T1 and T4 have the significance value (P-value): 0.127 and 0.252 which are greater than alpha (.05) value, thus null hypothesis is accepted.

For Thread Type T2 and T3, the significance value (P-value): 0.004 and 0.002 which are less than alpha (.05) value, thus null hypothesis is rejected.

Decision: The null hypothesis is accepted for thread Type T1 and T4, which means there is no significant difference between thread type T1 and T4 with seam efficiency of stitch class 400 for PC blended apparel.

The null hypothesis is rejected for thread T2 and T3, which means there is significant difference between thread types T2 and T3 with seam efficiency of stitch class 400 for PC blended apparel.

Seam Efficiency:

The results from Table 3.10 showed the analysis the seam efficiency of fabric ID F in warp direction.

Comments: From One-way ANOVA we found that thread type T1 have the significance value(P-value): 0.878 which is greater than alpha (.05) value, thus null hypothesis is accepted.

For Thread Type T2, T3 and T4 have the significance value (P-value):0.011, 0.011 & .024 which are less than alpha (.05) value, thus null hypothesis is rejected.

Decision: The null hypothesis is accepted for thread T1 which means there is no significant difference between thread types T1 with seam efficiency of stitch class 400.

The null hypothesis is rejected for thread T2, T3 and T4, which means there is significant difference between thread type T2, T3 and T4 with seam efficiency of stitch class.

Table 3.10: CLASS 400, SEAM EFFICIENCY (WARP)

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
T1	Between Groups	1.332	1	1.332	.025	.878
	Within Groups	425.758	8	53.220		
	Total	427.090	9			
T2	Between Groups	1103.550	1	1103.550	10.760	.011
	Within Groups	820.452	8	102.556		
	Total	1924.002	9			
T3	Between Groups	277.097	1	277.097	10.943	.011
	Within Groups	202.570	8	25.321		
	Total	479.667	9			
T4	Between Groups	198.827	1	198.827	7.726	.024
	Within Groups	205.890	8	25.736		
	Total	404.716	9			

Table 3.11: CLASS 400, Seam Strength (FILLING)

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
T1	Between Groups	54.990	1	54.990	3.286	.107
	Within Groups	133.874	8	16.734		
	Total	188.864	9			
T2	Between Groups	96.534	1	96.534	30.792	.001
	Within Groups	25.081	8	3.135		
	Total	121.615	9			
T3	Between Groups	35.006	1	35.006	2.473	.154
	Within Groups	113.246	8	14.156		
	Total	148.252	9			
T4	Between Groups	17.240	1	17.240	1.782	.219
	Within Groups	77.386	8	9.673		
	Total	94.625	9			

The results from Table 3.11 showed the analysis the seam strength of fabric ID F in filling direction.

Comments: From One-way ANOVA we found that thread Type T1, T3 and T4 have the significance value (P-value): 0.107, 0.154 and 0.219 which is greater than alpha (.05) value, thus null hypothesis is accepted.

For Thread Type T2, the significance value (P-value): 0.001 is less than alpha (.05) value, thus null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 3.12: CLASS 400, SEAM EFFICIENCY (FILLING)

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
T1	Between Groups	335.241	1	335.241	6.726	.032
	Within Groups	398.748	8	49.843		
	Total	733.989	9			
T2	Between Groups	35.759	1	35.759	2.113	.184
	Within Groups	135.357	8	16.920		
	Total	171.116	9			
T3	Between Groups	99.351	1	99.351	3.768	.088
	Within Groups	210.956	8	26.369		
	Total	310.307	9			
T4	Between Groups	129.025	1	129.025	7.753	.024
	Within Groups	133.130	8	16.641		
	Total	262.154	9			

Decision: The null hypothesis is accepted for thread Type T1, T3 and T4, which means there is no significant difference between thread type T1, T3 and T4 with seam strength of stitch class 400 for fabric F.

The null hypothesis is rejected for thread T2, which means there is significant difference between thread types T2 with seam strength of stitch class 400 for fabric F.

The results from Table 3.12 showed the analysis the seam efficiency of fabric ID F in filling direction.

Comments: From One-way ANOVA we found that thread Type T2 and T3 have the significance value (P-value): 0.184 and 0.088 which are greater than alpha (.05) value, thus null hypothesis is accepted.

For Thread Type T1 and T4 the significance value (P-value): 0.032 & .024 which are less than alpha (.05) value, thus null hypothesis is rejected.

Decision: The null hypothesis is accepted for thread T2 and T3 which means there is no significant difference between thread types T2 and T3 with seam efficiency of stitch class 400 for fabric F.

The null hypothesis is rejected for thread T1 and T4, which means there is significant difference between thread type T1 and T4 with seam efficiency of stitch class 400 for fabric F.

CONCLUSION

One types of deformation were observed in this study which is rupture of the stitching line (sewing thread breakage) for both Warp and filling directions. Overall, All stitch has higher seam strength and seam efficiency in warp direction compared to filling direction. Among four types of sewing thread below results are observed:

1) T4 thread shows better seam strength and Seam Efficiency for all four stitch types which is made from Polyester-wrapped thread with a polyester filament core thread.

2) T3 threads shows poor Seam Strength and Efficiency for four types of Stitch which is made from 100% cotton.

4) T1 threads shows average Seam Strength and Efficiency for All four types of Stitch for three fabrics which is made from 100% spun polyester.

Among two classes of stitch below findings are observed.

1) Stitch type 301 shows better strength and Efficiency compared to stitch type 304 for PC blended fabric.

2) Stitch type 401 shows better strength and Efficiency compared to stitch type 406 for PC blended fabric.

The statistical analysis proved the significant effect of the stitch types on the seam strength at significant level for PC blended apparel. It is vary for different thread types and different stitch classes. The outcome of this current research has the following basic conclusions. Seam strength and efficiency may depend on the thread type and stitch types for various cotton and Polyester cotton blended fabric. This is obvious in this study where performed Polyester-wrapped thread with a polyester filament core thread. It's prominent that the strength and efficiency produced by Polyester-wrapped thread with a polyester filament core thread might be the best performance of seams when used in stitching with specific stitch densities in apparel. This study has also asses the behavior of seams in the different stitch and threads of Polyester cotton blended fabric. It is said earlier in many references that stitch types, fabric type and thread type

have influence on the performance of seams in apparel. To sum up, it has provided information that the different thread types on the market produce different seam performances. Finally, this study is a document on the relations of stitch types and thread types on the overall performance of seams in apparel.

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